

Replication Paper:
What Caused the U.S. Pandemic-Era Inflation?
Blanchard and Bernanke (2023)

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Abstract

This paper replicates and extends the analysis of Blanchard and Bernanke (2023), who investigated the drivers of U.S. pandemic-era inflation by estimating a dynamic model of prices, wages, and both short- and long-run inflation expectations. Using the authors' replication package, the first objective is to confirm the robustness of their main results up to the second quarter of 2023. The second is to extend the dataset through the second quarter of 2025, incorporating updated information on wages, prices, expectations, and shortages. As in Blanchard and Bernanke, the estimated model is used to analyze both the direct and indirect effects of product- and labor-market shocks on prices and nominal wages. Consistent with their findings, the surge in inflation from 2021 was largely driven by price shocks relative to wages, including sharp increases in commodity prices and sector-specific spikes, reflecting strong aggregate demand on the one hand and supply constraints on the other. A key result concerns the more persistent impact of overheated labor markets on nominal wage growth and inflation compared to the transitory effects of product-market shocks. Extending the analysis through 2025 shows that while goods-market shocks largely faded after 2022, labor market tightness and wage dynamics remained important drivers of inflation. These results underscore both the robustness of the original framework and its relevance for understanding the subsequent disinflation period.

1 Introduction

1.1 The post-pandemic inflation and subsequent disinflation

The pandemic shock was marked by a sharp acceleration of inflation, which became one of the defining features of the crisis. The post-pandemic inflation surge of 2021–2022 was highly correlated across advanced economies, both in terms of timing and magnitude (Clarida, 2025). It was therefore not a phenomenon specific to the U.S., but a global event shaped by a sequence of common factors that empirical research continues to investigate. After decades in which inflation had remained subdued and consistently below target, prices began to rise rapidly in 2021, reaching peaks not observed since the 1970s. A growing body of applied

work suggests that three main forces were behind this surge. First, initial shocks to aggregate supply (Ball et al., 2022; Bernanke and Blanchard, 2024; Clarida, 2023, 2024). Second, an endogenous policy response that operated as a correlated shock to aggregate demand (Shapiro, 2022; Clarida, 2023). And third, a shift in relative demand from services to goods, which produced a significant increase in the equilibrium relative prices of goods relative to services (Afrouzi et al., 2024). With regard to adverse supply shocks, it is well established that the pandemic deeply disrupted labor markets and depressed labor force participation long after vaccines became available. A further exogenous supply shock occurred in 2022 with Russia’s invasion of Ukraine, which placed strong upward pressure on global energy and food prices (Clarida, 2025).

By June 2022, U.S. headline CPI inflation had reached 9.1 percent (before seasonal adjustment), the largest twelve-month increase since February 1981.¹ Over the same period, food at home index rose by 12.2 percent, energy prices rose by 41.6 percent, with gasoline index increasing by 59.9 percent, electricity about 13.7 percent, and natural gas 38.4 percent. Another important factor behind the subsequent inflation surge was the aggressive policy response implemented during the pandemic. Governments and central banks went “all in” with large-scale interventions to support their economies (Barro and Bianchi, 2024). Fiscal responses varied considerably across countries, ranging from the U.S. unprecedented stimulus of more than five trillion dollars to more modest packages elsewhere. By contrast, monetary policies were almost uniformly expansionary: policy rates were reduced to the effective lower bound, and quantitative easing programs were significantly expanded (English et al., 2021). The Federal Reserve, for example, lowered the federal funds rate to the 0–0.25 percent range and launched an open-ended quantitative easing program (Clarida, 2025). A third major driver of inflation was the unprecedented shift in relative demand from services, such as travelling, toward durable goods, including furniture and electronics. This dramatic reallocation of expenditure, interacting with supply chain bottlenecks, caused goods prices to rise sharply. As Clarida (2025) notes, when the equilibrium price of goods rises, the overall price level will adjust upward unless offset by a decline in services prices. However, in this event, central banks initially opted to accommodate the price pressure by not trying to offset the increase in the relative prices of goods (Steinsson, 2024). In fact, no advanced economy inflation-targeting central bank raised interest rates before inflation had exceeded its target, a delay that drew widespread criticism. Nonetheless, a number of economists, including Blanchard and Bernanke (2023), argue that central banks acted reasonably given the extraordinary uncertainty at the time, and that a more accurate foresight was virtually impossible in the face of the unprecedented pandemic shock.

However, even if initially slow to respond, central banks ultimately raised interest rates and, aided by the reversal of the supply shocks that had fueled the initial surge, succeeded in bringing inflation down to what was often described as “two-point-something.” By the summer of 2024, confidence in the disinflation process was strong enough that several central banks began cutting policy rates (Clarida, 2025). By the end of 2024, inflation in most advanced economies had declined to below 3 percent, long-term expectations appeared firmly anchored at target, and monetary authorities expressed confidence that the disinflationary

¹Bureau of Labor Statistics, Consumer Price Index News Release, June 2022.

trend would continue.

By the second quarter of 2025, the U.S. Employment Cost Index (ECI) indicated that total compensation was rising at a pace consistent with a gradual alignment between wage dynamics and a lower-inflation environment. Compensation costs for private industry workers increased by 3.5 percent over the year, with wages and salaries also up to 3.5 percent for the twelve months ending in June. The cost of benefits rose by 3.4 percent over the same period, while inflation-adjusted (constant-dollar) wages and salaries registered a 0.8 percent increase.² At the same time, the labor market showed clear signs of cooling from previously tight conditions. Job openings fell back to more normal levels (about 7.4 million in June 2025), quits declined, and the Beveridge curve shifted inward, suggesting a reduced imbalance between labor demand and supply. Inflation measures confirmed the disinflationary trend. On a twelve-month basis, headline CPI slowed to 2.7 percent in June 2025, following a 2.4 percent increase in May. The energy index fell by 0.8 percent over the year, while the food index rose by 3.0 percent.³ The resulting configuration fits a standard disinflation pattern rather than outright deflation: the pace of price increases declined substantially, yet the aggregate price level continued to rise.

Thus, by 2024 mid-2025, the economy had entered a disinflation phase characterized by near-target headline inflation and core measures still above 2 percent but on a downward path, with with the remaining stickiness concentrated in shelter and select services. This trajectory is consistent with the view that goods-market shocks accounted for much of the initial surge, while the persistence observed in 2023–2025 reflected the slower adjustment of wages and services prices as labor-market tightness gradually receded.

1.2 The post-pandemic inflation debate: a brief overview

Over the past three decades, inflation was widely regarded as a solved problem in advanced economies. From the early 1990s to the outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic, price stability was largely taken for granted, sustained by the credibility of central banks and by the structural transformations that characterized the era of so-called “great moderation.” The sudden resurgence of inflation in 2021, after the pandemic, which had not been anticipated by central banks or major financial institutions, quickly became a macroeconomic concern across developed capitalist economies (Martins, 2024). Within a short period, the United States and Europe experienced price dynamics not seen for four decades, forcing a rapid reappraisal of analytical frameworks and policy prescriptions. The debate that followed has largely crystallized around two broad perspectives: the neoclassical view and the critical political economy view. These perspectives differ in their interpretation of the origins of the inflationary process, the mechanisms through which it propagated, and the remedies required to restore price stability.

The neoclassical-inspired view, though expressed in different variants, converges on the central idea that inflation propagates either through excess demand (or a positive output gap

²Bureau of Labor Statistics, Employment Cost Index News Release, June 2025.

³Bureau of Labor Statistics, Consumer Price Index News Release, June 2025.

scenario) or through the unanchoring of inflationary expectations. This perspective remains dominant in policy institutions and much of academic economics and is typically articulated in three strands: the monetarist or “unconditional demand” view, the conditional excess demand view, and the central bank view. All three strands share the assumption that recent inflation reflects an excess of aggregate demand, in which *ex ante* planned consumption and investments exceed the productive capacity of the economy, thereby exerting upward pressure on prices (Martins, 2024). They differ, however, in how they account for the sources of this excess demand, ranging from expansive fiscal and monetary policies, to policy misdiagnosis of the recovery, to the role of expectations.

The Monetarist view, often considered the strictest and least widely embraced, asserts that inflation is the direct consequence of a significant expansion of the money supply. From this perspective, central banks should allow the money supply to grow at a stable rate, refraining from using monetary policy as a stabilization tool, since any injection of money is ultimately expected to generate a generalized increase in prices in the long run. In other words, monetarists stress the unconditional role of monetary and fiscal expansions (unless offset by tax increases) in fueling inflation, emphasizing the connection between pandemic-related stimulus and the subsequent surge in prices.

The conditional excess demand view argues that post-pandemic inflation emerged because central banks and governments misdiagnosed the nature of the recession and implemented inappropriate policies. Drawing a parallel with the Great Financial Crisis of 2007–2008, policymakers assumed that a sequence of prolonged expansionary monetary and fiscal interventions would be necessary to support a slow recovery. Yet these expectations did not materialize: after an initial sharp contraction, advanced economies experienced a rapid rebound, due only in part to policies that sustained employment and household income (Martins, 2024). In this context, expansionary interventions are seen as having contributed significantly to the inflationary surge. The “conditionality” in this approach refers to the idea that demand generated by policy is not inherently inflationary, in contrast to the Monetarist view. Rather, inflation is understood as the outcome of a mistaken diagnosis of the economy position relative to its productive potential. Summers (2022) argues that central banks maintained stimulus programs for too long, ignoring clear signs of recovery. Similarly, Bernanke (2022), drawing on the experience of the 1970s, identifies demand-side forces as central drivers of the post-pandemic surge. In both episodes, inflation began to rise after a long period of stability, coinciding with ambitious fiscal spending plans. Thus, while supply shocks, particularly those affecting food and energy, played an important role, excessive demand fueled by fiscal and monetary injections is regarded as the primary source of inflationary pressures. Conversely, Furman (2022) and Comin et al. (2023) argue that the post-pandemic surge in inflation reflected the raise of a positive output gap. On the demand side, expansionary monetary policy contributed to an increase in aggregate spending, while on the supply side potential output was reduced by supply-chain disruptions and energy shocks. The interaction of stronger demand with constrained supply thus generated persistent inflationary pressures.

The central banks view, most closely associated with central banks themselves, focuses on

the anchoring of expectations. It rejects the idea that expansionary policies were responsible for triggering inflation, arguing their vital role in the recovery. Instead, the key driver of inflation has to be found in the persistent constraints in production chains and the rising costs of raw materials, particularly pronounced by the Ukrainian war. In other words, inflation is caused by external supply side shocks, rather than excessive aggregate demand.

Within the neoclassical camp, economists and scholars have often been divided into the so-called “team transitory” and “team persistent.” The former interprets post-pandemic inflation as a largely self-correcting process with weak propagation mechanisms, while the latter views it as a persistent phenomenon driven by stronger amplification channels. Among those in the persistent camp, three main subgroups can be identified, reflecting different interpretations of the roles played by expectations and labor markets in sustaining inflation. The first subgroup is represented by Monetarists, who emphasize a labor-market-based view of inflation, arguing that wage dynamics play a central role in inflation persistence. The second consists of New Keynesian scholars who maintain that labor market tightness contributed to unanchoring inflation expectations early in the post-pandemic stage, highlighting the role of excess demand in overheating the economy. The third subgroup takes a different stance: it argues that labor market conditions were not responsible for the initial propagation of inflation, nor was inflation inherently bound to escalate. Instead, the prolonged duration of supply-side shocks eventually weakened the anchoring of expectations, leading to persistence. In this context, central banks responded as best they could, given the information available at the time.

Blanchard and Bernanke (2023) position themselves within this broader framework, offering one of the most influential analyses in support of the persistent view. They stress that labor market overheating only became a driver later in the inflationary process, and thus played a relatively minor role in the initial surge. Their empirical model, based on a structural vector autoregression model (SVAR) applied to U.S. data, finds that product-market shocks, the reallocation of demand from services to durable goods, and expansive fiscal policy were the main initial drivers of inflation. However, they argue that these factors alone cannot explain the persistence of inflation after the pandemic, which is better explained by labor market tightness. In a subsequent contribution, Blanchard and Bernanke (2024) extended their framework to eleven economies, finding broadly consistent results across countries but also significant cross-country differences. This perspective aligns with the policy stance adopted by central banks by mid-2022. From May of that year, major central banks openly supported raising interest rates, even while still rejecting the idea that excess demand was the primary cause of inflation propagation.

In summary, the various strands of the neoclassical view converge, especially after the 2022 shift in monetary policy, on the idea that unanchored expectations represent the principal long-term risk for inflation persistence. At the same time, they continue to diverge in their interpretation of the origins of inflation and the precise role of monetary authorities in shaping its trajectory.

At the opposite pole, critical political economists argue for shifting attention to the

microeconomic and sectoral structure of the economy, examining how supply constraints translated into rising prices through input–output linkages and changes in firms’ pricing behaviour. Rather than attributing inflation primarily to excess demand, they emphasize that energy price increases, disruptions in global supply chains, and sectoral bottlenecks were the proximate causes of the inflationary surge. Yet, in their view, the persistence of high prices cannot be understood without taking into account profit margins, oligopolistic pricing power, and the dynamics of wage bargaining. Sector-specific shocks, particularly in utilities, raw materials, and agricultural products, spread rapidly through the economy due to strong intersectoral linkages, producing a cost-push inflationary process rooted in sectoral price dynamics (Weber et al., 2022). Similarly, Storm (2022) stresses the sectoral origins of inflation and highlights the interaction between supply bottlenecks and market power. Using input–output data, he concludes that the total increase in prices between the second quarter of 2020 and the first quarter of 2022 was mainly driven by higher non-labor input costs and rising corporate profits.

Although excess demand is rejected as the main explanation, this does not mean that demand is irrelevant (Martins, 2024). While the neoclassical view underscores the responsibility of expansionary policies, critical political economists focus on their impact on inequalities, pointing out that monetary injections disproportionately raised asset values and deepened wealth disparities among households. In this view, inflation is rooted in class conflict, triggered by specific shocks, and reflects structural contradictions within the capitalist system. Accordingly, post-pandemic inflation is not conceived primarily as a macroeconomic imbalance to be corrected at any cost, but rather as a distributive process requiring policies that mitigate persistence while promoting fairer outcomes. Policy recommendations therefore diverge sharply from neoclassical prescriptions. Instead of broad-based monetary tightening, the emphasis is placed on measures such as targeted taxation of windfall profits, strategic price regulation in critical sectors, and support for sustainable wage growth to prevent the erosion of household purchasing power. The objective is not only to bring inflation under control but to do so in a way that resolves distributive tensions without imposing disproportionate costs on workers.

This debate provides the essential background for the replication exercise undertaken in the following sections. By focusing on Blanchard and Bernanke’s influential model (2023), this study engages directly with the neoclassical strand that has shaped much of the policy response. At the same time, extending their analysis with data through the second quarter of 2025 allows to assess the robustness of their conclusions in light of the subsequent disinflation and to situate their findings within the wider spectrum of interpretations that still animates the debate on post-pandemic price fluctuations.

1.3 The study

Blanchard and Bernanke offer one of the most influential analytical illustrations of the persistence of inflation. Using U.S. time-series data, they investigate the origins of post-pandemic inflation through a simplified model comprising four behavioural equations: a wage equation, a price equation, and two equations for short-run and long-run inflation expectations.

To capture labor market tightness, they employ the vacancy-to-unemployment ratio, which they argue is more appropriate for the post-Covid macroeconomic environment. This framework allows them to estimate both the direct and indirect effects of product-market and labor-market shocks on prices and nominal wages. Their results indicate that product-market shocks, such as supply-chain disruptions, the reallocation of demand from services to durable goods, and fiscal expansion, were the primary drivers of inflation in its initial phase. However, these factors alone cannot account for the persistence of inflation after the pandemic. Instead, they attribute the later inflationary pressures to labor market tightness. In other words, the impact of overheated labor markets on nominal wage growth and inflation proved more persistent than the effects of product-market shocks. As they state:

Labor market overheating would indeed ultimately prove to be a source of persistent inflation. [...] Beyond the more-familiar (but unexpectedly large and sustained) shocks to food and energy prices, the pandemic itself led to unusual distortions in key product markets, such as those for new and used vehicles. Strong aggregate demand and shifts in the composition of consumer spending (e.g., from services to durable goods) during the pandemic combined with constraints on supply in some sectors to create shortages and sectoral price increases not offset by decreases in other sectors (Guerrieri et al., 2022; di Giovanni et al., 2023). These sectoral mismatches between demand and supply proved more intractable and longer-lasting than many had expected. Together, these shocks to prices given wages would prove to be the critical triggers of the rise in inflation. This is the story we develop in this paper.

They estimate an empirical version of the simplified model, incorporating a lag structure to capture flexible dynamics, and use these estimates to decompose inflation into the effects of several shocks. This decomposition accounts for general equilibrium effects, time lags, and linkages among alternative sources of inflation. Their analysis ends in the second quarter of 2023, precisely as U.S. inflation began to recede. This replication paper therefore has two purposes. First, it tests the reproducibility of their results using the authors' replication package. Second, it extends the dataset through the second quarter of 2025 to evaluate whether their main conclusions remain valid during the subsequent disinflation phase. By comparing the original estimates with updated results, the paper seeks to assess the robustness and policy relevance of their framework, while situating their findings within the broader spectrum of interpretations that continue to shape the debate on post-pandemic inflation.

2 Replication

2.1 Data and Methodology

The original dataset employed by the authors covers the period 1989Q1–2023Q2, with estimations beginning in 1990Q1 on a quarterly basis. All replication exercises in this study rely on the replication package provided (path in Appendix). For the extension, all publicly available series were updated through the second quarter of 2025 (2025Q2). Public data sources include the Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis (FRED) database, the Bureau of Labor Statistics (BLS), the Bureau of Economic Analysis (BEA), and Google Trends. Proprietary Bloomberg data were used only in the original paper for the principal component

analysis (PCA) of commodity prices; these data were not employed in either the replication or the extension. All code and supplementary materials for both replication and extension are available upon request. The equations of the model are briefly reported here without reproducing the empirical derivations, for which the reader is referred to the original study by Blanchard and Bernanke.

Their approach is aggregative: the model does not incorporate microeconomic determinants or sectoral foundations of price changes, such as industry-specific factors. Instead, it relies on four behavioural equations that jointly determine nominal wages, prices, and both short-run and long-run inflation expectations. To capture flexible dynamics, the specification includes four quarterly lags as well as proxies for supply shocks. Two datasets are employed: a full sample, which includes the pandemic period and is used to estimate the baseline price equation, and a pre-Covid sample covering 1990Q1–2019Q4.

The three equations for wage growth and inflation expectations are estimated only on the pre-pandemic sample, ending in 2019Q4. The reason is that these specifications are intended to capture structural relationships, such as the sensitivity of wage growth to labor market slack, or the responsiveness of short and long-run expectations to actual inflation, that are best identified in a period of relative stability. The Covid-19 shock, with its combination of unprecedented supply disruptions, massive fiscal and monetary interventions, and abrupt changes in labor market dynamics, represents a structural break that could distort these coefficients if included in the estimation sample. Restricting the estimation window to the pre-pandemic years allows the parameters to be interpreted as underlying behavioral elasticities, which can then be applied to the extraordinary period that followed. By contrast, the price inflation equation is estimated on the full sample. In this case, rather than identifying stable behavioral parameters, the purpose is to account for the actual dynamics of prices during and after the pandemic and to decompose inflation into its main drivers. Including data through the pandemic years allows the regression to capture the role of energy and food shocks, shortages, wages, and expectations in explaining observed inflation. Once the parameters are estimated, the model is used to generate projections. The wage and expectations equations, though estimated on data ending in 2019Q4, are simulated forward with observed values of their explanatory variables, producing predicted paths through the pandemic and post-pandemic years. In this replication exercise, the projections are extended to 2025Q2, incorporating the most recent data. The price equation, estimated directly on the full sample, is likewise used to generate predicted versus actual inflation paths over the same horizon.

2.1.1 The aggregate wage equation

Standard assumptions are made, namely that nominal wages depend on the expected price level and on the degree of labor market tightness. More specifically, the nominal wage w in each quarter depends on the expected price for that quarter p^e , a real aspiration wage ω^A and an indicator of labor market tightness x :

$$w = p^e + \omega^A + \beta x \tag{1}$$

Aspiration real wage ω^A is used as a variable expressed in real terms, in contrast to the nominal wage w , and with the aim to model a possible catch-up effect ⁴ or considering it as a long-run equilibrium real wage. Aspiration real wage in each quarter is assumed to be a weighted average of the previous quarter aspiration wage and realized real wage, plus a shock term z_ω , that captures all the factors affecting wage determination:

$$\omega^A = \alpha\omega^A(-1) + (1 - \alpha)(w(-1) - p(-1)) + z_\omega \quad (2)$$

α is the parameter capturing the catch-up effect, which may be either zero or different from zero. In the first case, the change in nominal wages corresponds to the expected rate of inflation in the previous quarter, plus a term reflecting labor market tightness x , resulting in a standard expectations-augmented wage Phillips curve. When α is different from zero, the catch-up term measures the deviation between the previous and the current price level. Its economic implication is that workers seek compensation for the unexpected inflation of the last period, thereby influencing the bargaining process. This mechanism introduces a degree of real wage rigidity.

Wages, prices and expected prices are expressed in logarithmic scale, in order to interpret their differences as growth rates.

2.1.2 The aggregate price equation

Standard assumption that price level p depends on the level of nominal wages, plus a shock term z_p that captures the relative costs of non-labor inputs, variations in markups and other factors affecting price determination, is made. In first differences:

$$p - p(-1) = (w - w(-1)) + (z_p - z_p(-1)) \quad (3)$$

2.1.3 Inflation expectations equations

Short-run inflation expectations are a weighted average of long-run inflation expectations (π^*) and last period inflation:

$$p^e - p(-1) = \delta\pi^* + (1 - \delta)(p(-1) - p(-2)) \quad (4)$$

Long-run inflation expectations are a weighted average of last period long-run inflation expectations and actual inflation:

$$\pi^* = \gamma\pi^*(-1) + (1 - \gamma)(p(-1) - p(-2)) \quad (5)$$

δ and γ parameters capture the anchoring degree of short-run and long-run expectations, respectively. The first represents the degree to which price inflation affects wage inflation: the lower, the more persistent the dynamic effect of a price shock. The second, conversely, expresses the effect of transitory shocks on long-run inflation. As authors state, the value of π^* at any point in time is determined by the history of inflation. An episode of higher

⁴a situation in which workers try to make up for past losses of purchasing power, implying a certain degree of rigidity in real wage.

Figure 1: Replication: Responses of inflation to a price shock for alternative parameter choices

inflation leads to higher steady-state inflation. The longer the episode (or the lower γ), the stronger the effect on steady-state inflation.

The empirical steps implemented follow the original analysis: a set of structural autoregression SVAR of wage and price equations is conducted using STATA software. The conditional forecasts and impulse responses are implemented using Dynare in MATLAB software, while the construction of shortage indices is done with R. And finally, the decomposition of inflation into supply, demand and expectations is tested.

Considering all the four equations, when the aspiration wage is substituted out, the model determines the evolution of four endogenous variables: π^* , p^e , w and p .

2.1.4 Inflation simulation

A preliminary simulation of the full model is conducted under the assumption that the price shock z_p increases permanently by one unit in the first period. Two cases are considered. In the first, a limited catch-up effect and stable inflation expectations are assumed, by setting $\alpha = 0.2$, $\delta = 0.9$, and $\gamma = 0.95$. Consistent with the original results, Figure 1 shows that the sharp increase in inflation following the price shock is gradually absorbed and almost completely reversed after a few periods (blue line, weak feedback). In this case, inflation is not persistent, reflecting a situation in which workers are unable to fully offset unexpected inflation in their wage bargaining (weak catch-up), while expectations remain well anchored. Inflation eventually settles at a level slightly above zero, around 0.1 percent.

In the second case, with a stronger catch-up effect and less anchored expectations ($\alpha = 0.6$, $\delta = 0.7$, and $\gamma = 0.9$), the dynamics generate a price–wage spiral: higher prices trigger stronger nominal wage demands, which in turn sustain higher prices, leading to more persistent inflation. In the long-run inflation resulting from a one-time price shock is not negligible in such a framework. Thus, while weak catch-up and well-anchored expectations allow central banks to look through temporary shocks, a strong feedback mechanism combined with less stable expectations requires a robust policy response.

A second simulation considers the effects of a permanent one-unit increase in labor market tightness. After an initial rise, inflation continues to increase as long as labor market conditions remain overheated. As shown in Figure 2, the pace of this increase depends on the degree of expectations anchoring and the strength of the catch-up effect. In the case of

Figure 2: Replication: Responses of inflation to a permanent increase in labor market tightness for alternative parameter choices

well-anchored expectations and weak feedback, a tight labor market results in a gradual and moderate increase in inflation (blue curve). By contrast, when wage rigidities and less stable expectations are introduced, the effects of tightness on both wages and prices are amplified (red curve). As the authors note, the longer the overheating episode, the stronger the role of catch-up. Likewise, the weaker the anchoring of expectations, the larger the impact of labor market tightness on inflation, and the greater the monetary contraction required to bring inflation back to target, *ceteris paribus*.

Therefore, when an economy is hit by a large and permanent price shock, the resulting surge in inflation will be strong but temporary. Its persistence depends primarily on the anchoring of expectations, on the one hand, and on the degree of real-wage rigidity, on the other. By contrast, when the economy experiences sustained overheating in the labor market, inflation increases more slowly but persistently, at a pace determined by the sensitivity of wages to labor market tightness and by the stability of expectations.

For clarity, the set of endogenous and exogenous variables is reported below, while further details can be found in the Appendix section of the original paper.

Endogenous variables

- *gp*: price inflation, measured by quarterly annualized rates of change in the Consumer Price Index (CPI)
- *gw*: growth rate of nominal wages, quarterly and annualized, measured by the rate of change in the Employment Cost Index (ECI)
- *cf1*: short-term inflation expectations, measured by one-year inflation expectations
- *cf10*: long-term inflation expectations, measured by the Federal Reserve ten-year inflation expectations series
- *catch-up*⁵: a linear combination of past *gp* and *cf1*

Exogenous variables

⁵Catch-up is represented by the losses to workers' purchasing power due to inflation, measured by the four- quarter average of CPI inflation minus the one-year inflation expectation four quarters earlier.

- *grpe*: growth rate of the relative price of energy, quarterly and annualized, measured as the rate of change of the ratio of CPI energy prices to the ECI
- *grpf*: growth rate of relative price of food, quarterly and annualized, measured as the rate of change of the ratio of CPI food prices to the ECI
- *v/u*: ratio of job vacancies to unemployment
- *shortage*: an index of supply chain bottlenecks
- *gpty*: trend productivity growth, measured by the eight-quarter moving average of log changes of nonfarm business value added divided by nonfarm employee hours

3 Results

The replication of the analysis lead overall to the same results and conclusions of the original work. As Blanchard and Bernanke conclude, goods shocks dominated at the early stages of the crisis, in 2021, while labor market tightness gained importance later in 2022–’23. Minor discrepancies arose in the code, available upon request.

3.1 The wage equation

In the first equation, wage growth *gw* is regressed on a constant, four quarterly lags of itself, four lags of of short-run inflation expectations *cf1*, four lags of the unexpected inflation term *catch-up*, four lags of our proxy for labor market tightness *v/u*, and one lag of trend productivity growth *gpty*. To ensure the long-run Phillips curve is vertical, an homogeneity assumption is imposed, i.e. the sum of coefficients on lagged nominal wage growth and lagged short-run expectations equals one.

Table 1: Wage growth regression, restricted sample. Dependent variable: *gw*

Independent variable	gw	v/u	catch-up	cf1	gpty
<i>Lags</i>	-1 to -4	-1 to -4	-1 to -4	-1 to -4	-1
Sum of coefficients	0.460	0.693	-0.024	0.540	0.031
<i>p</i> -stat (sum)	0.008	0.030	0.765	0.002	0.608
<i>p</i> -stat (joint)	0.071	0.023	0.994	0.022	0.608
R-squared					0.578
No. observations					120

Notes: Pre-Covid sample used (1990Q1- 2019Q4). “Sum of coefficients” sums the lag coefficients indicated in the *Lags* row. “*p*-stat (sum)” reports the *p*-value for the null hypothesis that the sum of coefficients equals zero; “*p*-stat (joint)” is the joint significance test of each corresponding lag block.

Table 2: Wage growth regression, full sample. Dependent variable: *gw*

Independent variable	<i>gw</i>	<i>v/u</i>	<i>catch-up</i>	<i>cf1</i>	<i>gpty</i>
<i>Lags</i>	-1 to -4	-1 to -4	-1 to -4	-1 to -4	-1
Sum of coefficients	0.559	0.694	-0.013	0.441	0.035
<i>p</i> -stat (sum)	0.000	0.007	0.826	0.002	-
<i>p</i> -stat (joint)	0.001	0.000	0.768	0.035	0.530
R-squared					0.654
No. observations					142

Notes: full sample used (1990Q1- 2025Q1). “Sum of coefficients” sums the lag coefficients indicated in the *Lags* row. “*p*-stat (sum)” reports the *p*-value for the null hypothesis that the sum of coefficients equals zero; “*p*-stat (joint)” is the *p*-value for the joint hypothesis that each of the lag coefficients separately equals zero.

As previously noted, the wage equation is estimated over the pre-covid sample in order to avoid distortions from the disruptive effects of the pandemic, which could bias the estimates. For this reason, the replication follows the same approach as the original study, confirming identical results for the restricted sample. For comparability, however, and while acknowledging the potential distortions arising from exogenous shocks, Table 2 reports the estimates obtained from the full sample, only with the purpose to allow a direct comparison with the pre-pandemic estimates. These estimates should therefore be interpreted with caution, as they are not exempt from potential biases, whereas those in Table 1 are based on a period of relative stability and thus are less affected by exogenous shocks.

The extended-sample regression up to 2025Q2 (Table 2) confirms the main insights of the baseline estimation, but with some important differences in magnitude and statistical significance with respect to the restricted sample (Table 1). The vacancy-to-unemployment ratio, the proxy adopted for labor market pressure, still exerts a significant effect on wage growth, with a sum of coefficients estimated at 0.694, a negligible difference with respect to the restricted sample (0.693). In this case, both the sum and joint tests yield a highly statistical significance, underscoring the robustness of the Phillips curve relationship even after the inclusion of the pandemic and post-pandemic years. Taken together with the sum of lagged nominal wage growth (0.559), this implies that an increase in *v/u* from 1.0 to 1.5, holding constant other factors, would raise long-run nominal wage growth by approximately $0.5 \times 0.694 \div (1 - 0.559) = 0.79$ percentage points, slightly higher than in the reduced sample.

Short-run inflation expectations *cf1* remain a relevant determinant of wage growth, with a sum of coefficients equal to 0.441 and statistically significant (sum: 0.002, joint:0.035), suggesting that expectations became more influential in wage dynamics during the high-inflation years of 2021–2022, and their effect persisted into the disinflationary phase of late 2023 up to 2025.

Conversely, the catch-up term remains negligible (−0.013) and statistically insignificant, in line with the reduced-sample results. Productivity growth *gpty* still shows no significant impact, reinforcing the view that wages did not adjust mechanically to trend productivity

Figure 3: Actual and predicted wage growth over period 2020Q1-2025Q1, based on the wage equation estimated on the pre-covid sample.

and some of the effect may be absorbed by the constant term.

Overall, the extended estimation strengthens the conclusion that labor market tightness v/u and short-term expectations $cf1$ are the primary channels through which inflation propagated into wages. Compared to the reduced-sample analysis, the coefficients appear slightly stronger and more robust statistically, which likely reflects the inclusion of the extreme post-pandemic fluctuations. This suggests that the Phillips curve relationship did not weaken in the most recent years.

Figure 3 compares actual and predicted wage growth between 2020Q1 and 2025Q1, capturing both the sharp acceleration in 2021–2022 and the subsequent moderation. The divergence between actual and predicted values is more pronounced during the early pandemic quarters, reflecting the extraordinary volatility of that period, but narrows significantly from mid-2022 onward, when both series converge around 3 to 4 percent. By early 2025, wage growth appears to stabilize at a level consistent with a disinflationary framework, suggesting once again that labor market tightness and expectations explain most of such dynamics.

3.2 The price equation

Price inflation, measured by the CPI, depends on nominal wage growth as well as on other factors that influence prices given wages, such as increases in non-labor input costs. The specification includes four lags of inflation and the current value plus four lags of wage growth. Because proprietary Bloomberg data were not available, it was not possible to conduct a principal component analysis (PCA) to extract a common factor for commodity prices. Nevertheless, it is well established that pandemic-era inflation was strongly influenced by unexpected increases in food and energy prices. Accordingly, the model incorporates the current values and four lags of both food price growth (grp_f) and energy price growth ($grpe$).

In addition to commodity prices, pervasive shortages of specific goods are considered another source of inflation. On the demand side, lockdowns shifted consumer spending away from services and toward durable goods. On the supply side, lockdowns disrupted global supply chains and transportation networks, generating constraints, bottlenecks, and capacity pressures in key sectors. The combined effect of stronger demand and limited supply resulted

Figure 4: Both cars and chips shortage are considered. Google searches are measured by an index, set at value 100 for 2021Q3 (vertical dotted line).

in a sharp acceleration in prices.

Figure 4 illustrates the central idea that shortages generate a fundamental asymmetry: price increases in certain sectors are not offset by price declines in others. The strength of this effect depends on the extent of the variation in relative demand or supply constraints. The automotive sector provides a clear example. U.S. vehicle production collapsed during the initial lockdowns but rebounded once factories reopened. By July 2020, assemblies were running at an annualized rate of about 12 million units, comparable to pre-pandemic levels (top panel). However, persistent shortages of semiconductors and other critical inputs subsequently constrained output, which dropped below 9 million units annually by the end of 2021. The other panels show that this contraction in supply did not reflect weak demand. Inventories of new vehicles fell to record lows as dealers struggled to meet demand (second panel), driving a sharp increase in new car prices (third panel). The bottom panel depicts Google search activity index in the U.S. for “chip shortage” and “car shortage,” both of which surged in 2021. The vertical dashed line (the threshold value of 100 of the designated index) at 2021Q3 marks the period during which automobile production hit its trough, inventories reached record lows, auto prices spiked, and, one quarter earlier, search activity peaked, all consistent with a shortage-driven price surge.

For price equation, price inflation gp is regressed on a constant, four lags of itself, the current value plus four lags of nominal wage growth gw , the current value plus four lags of inflation in the relative food and energy prices $grpe$, $grpf$, the current value plus four lags of shortage (based on Google trends), and one lag of productivity growth $gpty$. Provided $shortage$ is small during the pre-covid period, price equation is estimated on the full sample. As for the wage equation, homogeneity assumption holds, for which the coefficients on past price and on wage inflation sum to one.

Table 3 shows the results of the regression, on full sample. The relatively large sum of

Table 3: Price inflation regression, full sample. Dependent variable: gp

Independent variable	gp	gw	grpe	grpf	shortage	gpty
<i>Lags</i>	-1 to -4	0 to -4	0 to -4	0 to -4	0 to -4	-1
Sum of coefficients	0.343	0.657	0.066	0.120	0.013	-0.128
p -stat (sum)	0.027	0.000	0.000	0.053	0.320	-
p -stat (joint)	0.024	0.000	0.000	0.051	0.00	0.039
R-squared						0.942
No. observations						142

Notes: full sample used (1990Q1- 2025Q1). “Sum of coefficients” sums the lag coefficients indicated in the *Lags* row. “ p -stat (sum)” reports the p -value for the null hypothesis that the sum of coefficients equals zero; “ p -stat (joint)” is the p -value for the joint hypothesis that each of the lag coefficients separately equals zero.

coefficients on nominal wage growth (0.657) compared to the sum of coefficients on lagged inflation (0.343) confirms a rapid pass-through of wages to prices, consistent with the findings in the restricted sample. This suggests that wage dynamics remain a central driver of inflationary pressures even in the extended sample covering the disinflation phase of 2023–2025. In addition, relative energy and food prices also continue to affect inflation, though in different ways. The estimated long-run effect of an energy price shock, *ceteris paribus*, is $0.066 \div (1 - 0.343) = 10$ percent, closely in line with the earlier estimates and again larger than energy direct weight in the CPI basket, which indicates second-round effects of energy shocks on broader prices. By contrast, the sum of coefficients on food prices (0.120) is only marginally significant ($p = 0.053$), and, *ceteris paribus*, the implied long-run effect, $0.120 \div (1 - 0.343) = 18$ percent, remains above the direct CPI weight of food (14.4 percent, as obtained) but less precisely estimated than in the restricted sample. In line with the original findings, since wages are controlled for, over time there is a presence of some second round price effects of energy and food price shocks on the prices of other goods and services.

In line with the original regression results, the shortage variable continues to show an insignificant sum of coefficients (0.013, $p = 0.320$), but the joint test strongly rejects the null of the lag coefficients being each zero ($p = 0.000$). This pattern suggests that shortages still exert a strong but transitory effect on the price level: taken singularly, the lags wash out, but taken together they contribute significantly to inflation dynamics.

Finally, productivity growth enters with the expected negative sign (-0.128) and is jointly statistically significant ($p = 0.039$), supporting the view that higher productivity mitigates price pressures by reducing unit labor costs.

Overall, these results confirm the main conclusions drawn from the restricted sample, especially the central role of wages and the indirect amplification effect of energy and food shocks, while also indicating that, in the post-2023 disinflationary context, the influence of food prices appears slightly weaker and the effect of shortages remains essentially temporary rather than persistent.

Figure 5: Actual and predicted inflation over period 2020Q1-2025Q1, based on the price equation estimated over the full sample.

The estimated equation can once again be used to project the inflation path over time. As shown in Figure 5, the model predicts a peak in 2023Q3, whereas the observed data follow a smoother trajectory. This may reflect the gradual adjustment of model-based predictions to the disinflationary phase that began in early 2024. After the sharp decline in 2022, inflation stabilizes between 2 and 4 percent, gradually converging toward target-consistent levels. Compared with the original sample, the extension through the first quarter of 2025 underscores the transition from a phase of high and volatile inflation to one of greater stability, consistent with an ongoing disinflation process.

3.3 Inflation expectations equations

3.3.1 Short-run

Inflation expectations can be measured in several ways, this study follows the Federal Reserve’s construction of one-year (short-run) and ten-year (long-run) expectations. For short-run expectations, four lags are included in the specification to allow for gradual adjustment over time. In the estimated equation, short-run inflation expectations ($cf1$) are regressed on four lags of themselves, the current value plus four lags of long-run expectations ($cf10$), and the current value plus four lags of actual inflation. Once more, homogeneity restriction assumption, for which the sum of the coefficients of the three variables equals one, is imposed. This ensures that, in the long-run, a sustained increase in inflation is eventually matched by an equivalent increase in expectations. However, this restriction is less binding in the short-run, given that near-term expectations appear relatively well-anchored (Table 4). In practice, this implies that, *ceteris paribus*, short-term movements in inflation only modestly affect one-year expectations, although persistent inflationary episodes gradually feed through due to autocorrelation.

Indeed, short-run expectations are significantly influenced by their own past values (coefficient 0.369, $p = 0.014$). Long-run expectations show even greater persistence, with a sum of coefficients equal to 0.506, highly significant at the 1 percent level. In both cases, joint significance tests confirm the importance of lagged dynamics in explaining the evolution of expectations. By contrast, the impact of past inflation is smaller (coefficient 0.124), though

Figure 6: Actual and predicted short-run inflation expectations over period 2020Q1-2025Q1, based on the equation estimated on the restricted sample.

it remains statistically significant.

Table 4: Short-run inflation expectations. Dependent variable: $cf1$

Independent variable	$cf1$	$cf10$	gp
<i>Lags</i>	-1 to -4	0 to -4	0 to -4
Sum of coefficients	0.369	0.506	0.124
p -stat (sum)	0.014	0.000	0.001
p -stat (joint)	0.001	0.000	0.000
R-squared			0.908
No. observations			120

Note: restricted sample used (1990Q1-2019Q4). “ p -stat (sum)” is the p -value for the null that the sum of coefficients equals zero; “ p -stat (joint)” is the p -value for the joint hypothesis that each of the current and lag coefficients separately equals zero.

Figure 6 shows no evidence of de-anchoring, as the short-term effect of inflation on expected inflation does not appear to have increased. Expectations rose sharply during 2021–2022, peaking above 4 percent, before declining as inflationary pressures eased. From mid-2023 onwards, expectations stabilized in the 2–3 percent range, indicating a re-anchoring following the disinflation phase. Consistently, the full-sample estimates of the regression equation (see Table 6 in the Appendix) yield a sum of coefficients on inflation (gp) equal to 0.137, very close to the restricted-sample value of 0.124. This further supports the conclusion that short-run expectations remained anchored despite the temporary surge in inflation.

3.3.2 Long-run

Long-run expectations are regressed on four lags of themselves and on the current plus four lagged values of realized inflation. As in the short-run specification, the homogeneity restriction is imposed, requiring that the sum of coefficients equals one. Table 5 and Figure 7

Figure 7: Actual and predicted long-run inflation expectations over period 2020Q1-2025Q1, based on the equation estimated on the restricted sample.

suggest that long-run expectations remained well anchored, both during the pandemic and in the subsequent period. Specifically, there is no evidence of de-anchoring: in the full sample, the sum of coefficients on current and lagged inflation is estimated at 0.027, only slightly above the 0.025 obtained in the pre-Covid sample (see Table 7 in Appendix). The high estimated persistence of long-run expectations indicates that a sustained increase in inflation is gradually reflected in higher long-term expectations, a pattern particularly evident until early 2023. This reflects the strong autocorrelation of long-term expectations: while they are slow to adjust, they respond steadily to prolonged deviations in actual inflation.

Table 5: Long-run inflation expectations. Dependent variable: $cf10$

Independent variable	cf10	gp
Lags	-1 to -4	0 to -4
Sum of coefficients	0.975	0.025
p -stat (sum)	0.000	0.208
p -stat (joint)	0.000	0.004
R-squared		0.931
No. observations		120

Note: restricted sample used (1990Q1-2019Q4). “ p -stat (sum)” is the p -value for the null that the sum of coefficients equals zero; “ p -stat (joint)” is the p -value for the joint hypothesis that each of the current and lag coefficients separately equals zero.

3.4 Impulse Response Functions

The estimated model can be used to compute impulse response functions (IRFs), which account for both the simultaneity and the lagged relationships among wages, prices, and inflation expectations. IRFs are estimated over the full model, with the aim of capturing

Figure 8: Full-model, dynamic responses of inflation to a one-standard-deviation positive shock to relative energy prices, relative food prices, and the shortage variable. Propagation simulation for 24 quarters.

not only the direct effect of a given shock but also its knock-on effects in subsequent periods. Starting from the steady state, a one-standard-deviation positive shock to three designated price variables (i.e. the relative price of energy, the relative price of food, and the shortage index) and the vacancy-to-unemployment ratio is considered. The volatility of the shocks is measured using the standard deviation of the data between 2020Q1 and 2020Q3; for further discussion of this choice, see the original paper. The shocks are propagated for 16 quarters, allowing their effects to be traced over time.

Extending the horizon of the impulse response analysis to 24 quarters, while keeping the standard deviation of the shocks unchanged, does not alter the calibration of the shocks themselves but allows a clearer assessment of their persistence and eventual dissipation. This can be interpreted as simulating the effects through 2025.

As shown in Figure 8, which shows the response of inflation to price shocks, the results remain consistent with the original 16-quarter horizon. The immediate, sharp effects dissipate rapidly in the quarter following the shock, although a small but sustained increase in inflation of around 0.1 percentage points remains. This long-term effect reinforces the idea that steady-state inflation is strongly shaped by its past dynamics. Once again, the results indicate limited real wage rigidity and well-anchored short- and long-run inflation expectations, which adjust only gradually to realized inflation. The low persistence can be interpreted either as a reflection of the Fed’s credibility in restoring inflation to target or as evidence of the system’s capacity for relatively rapid “self-recovery”.

Figure 9 displays a full-model simulation of the effects of a persistent tight labor market on inflation, following a one-standard-deviation increase in the vacancy-to-unemployment ratio. The initial irregular path reflects the direct impact of changes in v/u on the wage equation. Once these short-run effects fade, inflation rises gradually but steadily, driven both by the influence of labor market tightness on wages and by the feedback of inflation into short- and long-run expectations. In this simulation, inflation increases by about 0.7 percentage points after six quarters and by roughly 1.0 percentage point after twelve quarters, continuing thereafter at a pace of around 0.15 percentage points per year. This pattern is consistent with the weak-feedback scenario of Figure 2, where the relatively modest rate of

Figure 9: Full-model, dynamic responses of inflation to a one-standard-deviation positive shock to vacancy-to-unemployment ratio.

increase reflects weak catch-up effects and well-anchored expectations.

3.4.1 Price inflation decomposition

Because the model is linear, the IRFs of each endogenous variable, including the responses to the equation residuals, sum exactly to the realized value of the variable at each date. This property allows the estimated model and the associated IRFs for historical shocks to be used in decomposing the variation of any endogenous variable into its underlying sources.

Figure 10 reports the estimated sources of price inflation based on the extended sample, covering 2020Q1 to 2025Q1. Since residuals are not included, the sum of the estimated components does not coincide with realized inflation in each quarter.

The first relevant aspect is related to the contribution of the initial conditions: these remain roughly constant over time, suggesting that, absent the pandemic-era shocks, inflation would likely have remained stable below 3 percent throughout the period. Consistent with the original estimates, energy shocks, by far the most important, together with food price shocks, played a dominant role during the peak of the inflationary episode in 2021–2022. Energy shocks in particular drove both the sharp acceleration in late 2021 and the subsequent decline in the second half of 2022, while food shocks contributed most visibly during the early 2022 peaks.

Shortages also played a significant role, beginning in 2020 and remaining important through 2021, likely reflecting lockdown effects, with residual effects still visible in 2022. By contrast, the contribution of labor-market tightness, proxied by the vacancy-to-unemployment ratio, was limited in the early stages and became more clearly positive only from 2022 onward, though never emerging as the dominant driver of inflation dynamics.

From 2023 onward, following the sharp swings of 2022, the role of commodity shocks diminished substantially. Inflation dynamics during this period appear increasingly shaped by initial conditions and other residual factors, with shortages contributing only modestly in late 2024. The vacancy-to-unemployment ratio retained a small but persistent role in sus-

Figure 10: Decomposition of price inflation, based on full model and IRFs

Note: line shows actual inflation. Total net heights of the bars represent the forecast of inflation in each period, given initial conditions through 2019Q4. Grey portion of each bar shows contribution of pre-2020 data and contributions of productivity shocks. Coloured sub-boxes show general equilibrium, fully dynamic contribution of each exogenous variable to inflation in that period.

taining inflation during 2023–2024, consistent with the Phillips curve mechanism, although its magnitude remained limited compared to the earlier commodity shocks.

3.4.2 Wage inflation decomposition

Figure 11 provides further insight into the role of labor market tightness in shaping wage dynamics. As in the case of price inflation, the contribution of initial conditions remains stable, consistently below 3 percent. Shortages play only a minor role, with a slow but steady impact between 2021Q1 and the end of 2023; their effect then gradually declines, though it remains slightly positive through 2025.

Food and energy fluctuations are concentrated in the most delicate phase, between 2022 and mid-2023. By contrast, the most important contribution is associated with the vacancy-to-unemployment ratio (v/u), the proxy for labor market tightness. Its effect swings from negative in the period 2020Q2–2021Q2 to a sustained positive impact between 2021Q3 and 2023Q3, before displaying renewed oscillations from 2024 onwards.

Blanchard and Bernanke themselves note:

At least for the short run, policymakers were initially more right than wrong in arguing that tight labor markets would not generate high inflation, although in focusing on unemployment rates and total employment rather than the vacancy-to-unemployment ratio they did underestimate labor market tightness.

As a further confirmation of these findings, they also state:

The initial sources of the inflation were primarily shocks to prices given wages, including large energy price shocks and the surprisingly persistent shortages of cars and other durable goods. By raising inflation expectations, and to a smaller extent by creating a catch-up effect, these shocks ultimately affected wages as well as prices. However, over time a very tight labor market has begun to exert increasing pressure on inflation, pressure which our model predicts will continue to grow. Over the longer

Figure 11: Decomposition of wage inflation, based on full model and IRFs

Note: line shows actual wage growth. Total net heights of the bars represent the forecast of wage growth in each period, given initial conditions through 2019Q4. Grey portion of each bar shows contribution of pre-2020 data and contributions of productivity shocks. Coloured sub-boxes show general equilibrium, fully dynamic contribution of each exogenous variable to wage growth in that period.

run, then, the critics who worried about an overheated economy leading to inflation may be able to claim some vindication.

3.5 Conditional forecasts

This section first presents the original conditional projections proposed by Blanchard and Bernanke and then extends the exercise by generating projections of inflation under the same three alternative assumptions about the vacancy-to-unemployment ratio, with a slight adjustment and starting from 2025Q3. The purpose is to obtain projections through 2027Q2.

In their original work, the authors used the model to project the paths of price inflation and wage growth from 2023Q2 through 2027Q1, adopting the previous four quarters as initial conditions. Several assumptions are imposed. First, the natural or steady-state value of the vacancy-to-unemployment ratio (v/u^*) is set equal to 1.2, its level in 2019Q4, the last full pre-pandemic quarter in which inflation was stable. Second, food and energy prices are assumed to grow at the same rate as nominal wages, implying that $grpf$ and $grpe$ are both set to zero. Third, the shortage variable is fixed at an index value of 10, with its maximum value set to 100, and productivity growth is assumed to equal 1 percent. Fourth, equation residuals are set to zero. Finally, while the price equation is estimated over the full sample, the other three equations are estimated using the pre-pandemic sample.

Three projections are considered, corresponding to alternative assumed trajectories of the labor market and based on the following parameterization. Policy is assumed to reduce v/u gradually over eight quarters, starting from 2023Q2. The first scenario maintains v/u at 1.8. The second assumes a return to the pre-pandemic value of 1.2, while the third considers a further decline to 0.8. *Ceteris paribus*, lower values of v/u imply tighter monetary and fiscal policies. Inflation is measured using the CPI, and nominal wages by the ECI. Figure

Figure 12: Inflation projection for three paths of v/u , beginning from 2023Q1

Figure 13: Inflation projection for three paths of v/u , beginning from 2025Q3

12 shows the original forecast, while Figure 13 presents the updated projection starting from 2025Q3.

All else equal, keeping v/u close to 1.8, the level observed in 2023, does not bring inflation down; instead, as long-term expectations adjust upward, inflation drifts higher over time. Conversely, reducing the vacancy-to-unemployment ratio to its steady-state level of 1.2 within eight quarters brings CPI inflation to around 2.7 percent. A more restrictive scenario, with v/u falling to 0.8, lowers inflation close to 2 percent by the end of the horizon, with the downward trajectory continuing thereafter.

For the conditional forecast beginning in 2025Q3, the same assumptions on v/u are maintained. In particular, no further food or energy shocks are assumed ($grpe = 0$, $grpf = 0$), the shortage index is fixed at 10, productivity growth at 1 percent, and residuals are set to zero. These exogenous conditions are imposed for eight quarters, through 2027Q2, with the Covid-related dummies set to zero, as pandemic effects are no longer relevant.

As shown in Figure 13, a persistently high v/u ratio of 1.8 keeps inflation above 3 percent through 2027, while a gradual return to the steady-state value of 1.2 yields a more moderate path, with inflation fluctuating between 2.7 and 3.0 percent. By contrast, a sharper decline in v/u to 0.8 produces a faster convergence toward 2 percent, consistent with target levels by the end of the horizon. These results confirm that labor market tightness plays a central role in shaping medium-run inflation dynamics. A persistently tight labor market tends to sustain higher inflation, while a looser labor market supports gradual disinflation toward target-consistent levels.

Recall that, as authors stressed, conditional projections should not be interpreted as unconditional forecasts, but rather as plausible scenarios conditional on specific assumptions about the path of v/u , with all other exogenous variables held at their steady-state values.

4 Conclusions

Pandemic-era inflation has been a complex phenomenon with unprecedented effects not only on households and firms but also on the broader economy, revealing delicate interdependencies and disrupting established equilibria. In line with the neoclassical view, inflation largely reflected strong aggregate demand, which tightened labor markets to record-high vacancy-to-unemployment ratios. Yet, at least initially, although the wage Phillips curve was operative, inflation expectations did not de-anchor and there was little evidence of a wage–price spiral: workers were unable to secure nominal wage gains sufficient to offset unexpected price increases, implying a weak catch-up effect. Decompositions of inflation indicate that tight labor markets made only a modest contribution in the early stages. Instead, the initial surge was mainly driven by supply bottlenecks and the mismatch between increasing demand and constrained supply, which pushed commodity prices up relative to wages.

A noteworthy finding concerns the transitory nature of price shocks. Although short-run expectations rose sufficiently to place upward pressure on wages and prices, they remained well-anchored, consistent with a weak catch-up effect. As a result, the inflationary impact of these shocks was largely temporary, even if it did not vanish entirely. This outcome is reassuring, but since 2023 the cumulative effects of persistent labor market tightness have begun to cumulate.

The extended analysis confirms the robustness of Blanchard and Bernanke’s framework and supports their argument that, despite the disruptive character of the pandemic, existing models of wage–price dynamics can still capture the underlying complexity. The evidence further reinforces their conclusion that the U.S. inflation surge was initially driven by goods-market shocks but later increasingly sustained by wage dynamics, while also adding insight into the disinflationary phase of 2023–2025. It also highlights the persistence of wage-driven pressures beyond 2023.

The original paper emphasize the importance of labor market balance, and, in line with these findings, the updated results show that this factor remained determinant for the trend through mid-2025. Ultimately, policymakers must remain alert to the possibility that inflationary pressures may stem both from product markets, via unexpected input cost shocks or demand shifts colliding with inelastic supply, and from labor markets. These pressures can interact and be mutually reinforcing, but maintaining labor market balance should remain the central concern for monetary authorities committed to price stability.

5 Appendix

In the original analysis, some alternative specifications are computed: price inflation are estimated using both CPI and PCE (Table A2 of Blanchard and Bernanke’s Appendix); expectations are computed using the Survey of Professional Forecasters, instead of Fed’s forecasts (Table A3 of Appendix).

For a comprehensive treatment of the empirical derivations and model specifications, the reader is referred to Blanchard and Bernanke (2023).

Replication files are available at <http://www.nber.org/data-appendix/w31417>

Summplementary Tables

Table 6: Short-run inflation expectations, full sample. Dependent variable: *cf1*

Independent variable	cf1	cf10	gp
<i>Lags</i>	−1 to −4	0 to −4	0 to −4
Sum of coefficients	0.304	0.559	0.137
<i>p</i> -stat (sum)	0.022	0.000	0.000
<i>p</i> -stat (joint)	0.000	0.000	0.000
R-squared			0.907
No. observations			142

Note: full sample used (1990Q1-2025Q1). “*p*-stat (sum)” is the *p*-value for the null that the sum of coefficients equals zero; “*p*-stat (joint)” is the *p*-value for the joint hypothesis that each of the current and lag coefficients separately equals zero.

Table 7: Long-run inflation expectations, full sample. Dependent variable: *cf10*

Independent variable	cf10	gp
<i>Lags</i>	−1 to −4	0 to −4
Sum of coefficients	0.972	0.027
<i>p</i> -stat (sum)	0.000	0.020
<i>p</i> -stat (joint)	0.000	0.000
R-squared		0.930
No. observations		142

Note: full sample used (1990Q1-2025Q1). “*p*-stat (sum)” is the *p*-value for the null that the sum of coefficients equals zero; “*p*-stat (joint)” is the *p*-value for the joint hypothesis that each of the current and lag coefficients separately equals zero.

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